

SPECIFICITIES OF THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH IN DIFFERENT PROJECT TYPES OF HORIZON EUROPE CALL TOPICS

Factsheet

Focus

The European Union Horizon Europe calls launched under Cluster 6 (*Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment*) and mission "A Soil Deal for Europe" generally envisage **four main project types – Programme Co-fund Actions (CO-FUND), Research and Innovation Actions (RIA), Innovation Actions (IA), and Coordination and Support Actions (CSA)** (incl. Regular, Thematic, and Advisory Network CSAs). Many of those require the application of the multi-actor approach (MAA). Yet, proposal developers might not always be aware of the nuances in the MAA per project type, thus limiting the type-specific possibilities of reaping the full potential of the MAA and increasing the risk of type-specific MAA pitfalls.

Purpose

This factsheet provides basic insights into the key differences between the project types of the Horizon Europe Programme (HEU) regarding the MAA along with selected examples showing type-specific features. **Integrating the MAA into RIA, IA and CSA proposals with tailored levels of the various actors' engagement** can boost the project's impact.

Envisaged mission by project type:

RIA – generate new knowledge, improve understanding and explore feasibility

IA – develop, test and scale solutions

CSA – facilitate knowledge exchange, networking and policy impact

Technology readiness level by project type

RIA – TRL 3–7

IA – TRL 6–8

CSA – not applicable

Funding rates by project type

RIA – 100% for all types of actors

IA – 100% for non-profit and 70% for business actors

CSA – 100% for all types of actors

Role of the MAA by project type:

RIA – co-create research questions as well as design and validate findings with users

IA – pilot, test, deploy innovations in real-life settings

CSA – enable good practice sharing and stakeholder dialogue

Good to know

- There is an increasing commitment by the European Commission to integrate the MAA requirement in the EU Research and Innovation Framework Programmes, resulting in a **notable number of funded MAA projects**.
- Out of 82 Call Topics launched under the HEU Cluster 6 in 2025, 30 (**37%**) **Topics include the MAA as an eligibility criterion**. The Soil Mission 2025 Calls present 4 MAA Topics out of 13 (31%).
- The largest share of Cluster 6 MAA Call Topics are RIAs** (63%), followed by IAs (27%) and CSAs (10%). In the Soil Mission 2025 Calls, all MAA Call Topics are RIAs.
- The application of **MAA can also appear as a recommended (non-mandatory) approach** as featured by additional 9 Call Topics (4 IAs, 3 RIAs, 2 CSAs) in HEU Cluster 6 in 2025.

Figure 1: Number of approved MAA projects in H2020 and HEU by project type (status in October 2024).

Figure 2: Distribution of Call Topics with the MAA as eligibility criterion by project type in the HEU Cluster 6 in 2025.

Real-life project examples

RIA

Example: [RUSTIK](#)
[HEU 2022-2026]

IA

Example: [FARMTOPIA](#)
[HEU 2023-2026]

USEFUL TIP!

You find a list of all Thematic Network projects granted so far [here](#). If you apply for a multi-actor project, referring to earlier projects working on the same thematic field is recommended.

Four discrete types of CSAs

CSA #1 (General CSAs)

Example: [COCOREADO](#)
[HEU 2021-2024]

CSA #2 (Thematic Networks to compile and share knowledge ready for practice)

Example: [FarmBioNet](#)
[HEU 2025-2027]

CSA #4 (EU Advisory Networks)

Example: [AdvisoryNetPEST](#)
[HEU 2025-2029]

CSA #3 (Thematic Networks to broaden the outcomes of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups across borders)

Example: [NUTRI-KNOW](#)
[HEU 2023-2025]

Typical MAA actor motivations and issues per main project type

	Actor motivations	Challenging issues
RIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>SMEs</i> - unique selling points for their new products. ▪ <i>Researchers</i> - scientific publications and funding for PhD students. ▪ <i>Advisors</i> - first-hand information for clients, sharpened professional profiles, representation of producers' interests. ▪ <i>Sales cooperatives</i> - higher margins, improved market performance. ▪ <i>Environmental NGOs</i> - evidence of protecting natural resources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>SMEs vs. Academic partners</i> - data protection vs. open data. ▪ <i>Universities vs. Advisors</i> - communication of published results vs. early sharing of insights. ▪ <i>Advisors vs. Producer organisations</i> - paid consultancy services vs. optimisation of margins on the product market. ▪ <i>NGOs vs. SMEs</i> - engagement in non-profit sustainability solutions vs. commercial solutions.
IA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>SMEs</i> - competitive advantage on the market for the high TRL products. ▪ <i>Researchers</i> - advancement of applied research, development of new products, services or solutions. ▪ <i>Advisors</i> - engagement of clients in the early phase of the product's market introduction, enhanced business support. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Private vs. Public actors</i> - business development objectives vs. societal benefits. ▪ <i>Researchers vs. SMEs</i> - public demonstration of prototypes vs. market-ready solutions. ▪ <i>SMEs vs. Advisors</i> - individual vs. shared ownership of merits for joint product or service.
CSA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Researchers</i> - financial support for ongoing on-farm experimentation. ▪ <i>Communication consultants</i> - increased visibility and business reputation. ▪ <i>Advisors</i> - locally-adapted training material and courses for their clients. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Researchers vs. Communication partners</i> - prioritisation of scientific publications vs. practice-oriented materials. ▪ <i>Advisors vs. Academic and supporting partners</i> - prioritisation of consultancy services vs. project work.

Further information

- ❑ [Horizon Europe Cluster 6 Work Programmes](#)
- ❑ [PREMIERE MAA Q&A](#)
- ❑ [CARE4BIO annotated templates per action type](#)

About this factsheet and PREMIERE

Contact: anda.adamsone-fiskovica@bscresearch.lv
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